

Heavy metals adsorption using CDW adsorbents: A sustainable path for water purification

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ABSTRACT

Effective removal of heavy metals from water is crucial for human health and environmental protection, and adsorbents provide a sustainable, cost-effective treatment solution. This study is the first to investigate Low-Density Concrete (LDC) for removing selected heavy metals (Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+}) from water. The adsorbent was characterised using X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Fourier Transform Infrared spectrophotometry (FTIR), Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) analysis, X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis, and Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM). The One-Factor-at-A-Time (OFAT) method optimised the essential parameters affecting the metal removal. Eight different isotherm models were used to determine the adsorption parameters and elucidate the associated sorption mechanism. Then, its kinetic behavior and selectivity for decontamination were analyzed. The outcomes demonstrated that the adsorption capacities for Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Co^{2+} were 43.1, 23.5, and 15.2 mg g^{-1} , respectively. Moreover, the second-order kinetic rate constants for Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Co^{2+} were determined to be 1.99, 0.076, and 0.49 $\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$, respectively. As a novel contribution, the regeneration process of heavy metal adsorption is modelled by Thales-based theorem. In this study, synthetic wastewater was used, while regeneration conditions simulated industrial effluents to enhance real-world relevance. Finally, the applied construction and demolition waste (CDW) adsorbent is evaluated by Sustainable Material Management, EPA models. The isothermal modelling illustrated that the adsorption of Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} onto LDC wastes is done physically and on the heterogeneous surface as multilayer adsorption. The Thales-based model demonstrated that after nine cycles of adsorption and formal regeneration with acid, the LDC adsorbent consistently maintained lead concentrations below the World Health Organization (WHO) standard.

1. Introduction

Employing waste-based adsorbents (WBAs) can be beneficial to reduce decontamination costs and ensure continuity between solid waste management and water treatment programs (Alswat et al., 2023). In recent years, WBAs have increasingly been used as a cost-effective and environmentally friendly method to remove hazardous substances from water resources, including heavy metals (Gkika et al., 2022; Varada et al., 2019). Various natural materials, such as agriculture waste (Bai et al., 2023), coir pith (Stelte et al., 2023), clay (Santoso et al., 2023), leaves (Alswat et al., 2023), and walnut shell (Enache et al.,

2023), have been used as green adsorbents due to their high adsorption capacity, low toxicity, and cost-effectiveness. In addition, waste-based inorganic substances such as zeolite, dolomite and bentonite can be used as adsorbents for heavy metals removal from water (Alyasi et al., 2025; Gruszecka-Kosowska et al., 2017; Kumari et al., 2025; Lee and Jo, 2010).

Generally, WBAs are categorized into three sources: industrial waste, construction and demolition waste (CDW), and agricultural waste (Zhou et al., 2022). CDW refers to waste from construction, renovation, and demolition, including concrete, brick, sand and gravel (Jain, 2021; Yuan et al., 2011). CDW is considered one of the most essential types of WBAs,

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as it has the potential to promote the circular economy and sustainable development goals (Sharma et al., 2021). Waste management strategies for used concrete emphasize immobilization and stabilization, where binders or additives encapsulate hazardous leachates and enhance durability performance. Recycling converts CDW into recycled aggregate concrete through closed-loop processes, while reuse focuses on design for deconstruction, enabling structural components to be reapplied across life cycles. Together, these strategies reduce landfill burdens, conserve natural aggregates, and optimize life-cycle sustainability (Xia et al., 2020). The considerable quantity of CDW generated, along with its potential deployment as a WBA, emphasizes its role as a practical solution for hazardous substance removal (Sharma et al., 2021).

One of the new technologies in the construction business is lightweight concrete, which has the benefits of structural engineering. However, when consumption rises, waste output also increases, especially for materials like autoclaved aerated concrete (AAC) (Gheibi et al., 2022). AAC is a popular lightweight building material typically consisting of silica, sand, cement, lime, quartz, and aluminum powder (Walczak et al., 2015). Due to their lighter weight, these materials are often used as substitutes for traditional bricks in non-load-bearing and partition walls (Aliabdo et al., 2014). Recent estimates place global annual non-reinforced AAC production at around 450 million m³ (Abhilasha et al., 2023). In 2020, Germany generated over 1 million m³ of post-demolition AAC, while the United Kingdom contributed around 700,000 m³. Eastern Europe exhibited even higher volumes, with Poland producing approximately 1.8 million m³ and Russia about 3.9 million m³ in the same year. Projections indicate that Europe's post-demolition AAC volumes will nearly double over the next decade, rising from 12.3 million m³ to 22.0 million m³ (Steins et al., 2022). To lessen the environmental burden of AAC waste, methods for its valorization should be developed in accordance with the principles of Integrated Solid Waste Management (ISWM) (Marshall and Farahbakhsh, 2013). Reuse of CDW is an approach that can be implemented in countries with high levels of re-construction activity. By adopting CDW management strategies, developing countries can address the challenges of waste management and promote sustainable and circular construction practices that align with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (dos Reis et al., 2020). According to Lee et al. (2024), CDW can be effectively managed through several strategies, including reduction, reuse, recycling, incineration, and landfilling prioritizing the first three for environmental sustainability. Reduction focuses on optimized design and construction planning, while reutilization stresses selective deconstruction. Recycling repurposes concrete, plastics, wood, and metal wastes for construction materials or energy sources. Additionally, adsorption applications are highlighted, where certain CDW-derived materials, such as concrete fines or brick dust, are processed and used as low-cost adsorbents for removing pollutants from wastewater. These materials demonstrate significant potential for environmental remediation, offering a dual benefit of waste reduction and water purification. The appropriate method depends on material type, contamination level, and intended application.

Various methods are used for heavy metal removal from wastewater, including membrane, chemical, electric, and photocatalytic techniques. Among them, adsorption stands out for being cost-effective, technically mature, and environmentally friendly, though it has lower automation potential. It is widely favored for its simplicity, high efficiency, and ability to use low-cost adsorbents like industrial and construction wastes (Qasem et al., 2021).

Upon reviewing the literature, it is evident that various studies have been conducted on using CDW-based adsorbents to remove heavy metals from aquatic environments. For example, Coleman et al. (2005) investigated the efficacy of crushed concrete in removing three heavy metals (Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, and Pb²⁺) from water. Djeribi and Hamdaoui (2008) also explored using mixed cedar sawdust with crushed bricks as an adsorbent to remove Cu²⁺ from water resources. In addition, Bibi et al. (2015) assessed the potential of cement as an adsorbent for arsenic from water.

Furthermore, Tsai et al. (2019) employed an innovative approach by using an aluminosilicate composite derived from waste display panel glasses as an adsorbent for removing Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, and Ni²⁺ contaminants and investigating the underlying adsorption mechanism.

Praneeth et al. (2022) recently developed a novel cement-based mixture combined with biochar to remove several heavy metals. The study examined the interactions between different metals and evaluated the environmental protection potential of the adsorbent. Meanwhile, Yurk et al. (2022) investigated the effectiveness of concrete particles in removing Cu²⁺ and analyzed the hydromechanics of the process. In another study, Liu et al. (2022) produced a nano ecological recycled concrete (nano-ERC) with copper oxide nanoparticles to remove heavy metals, including As ions, Cd²⁺, Mn²⁺ and Pb²⁺ from simulated wastewater effluent. Recycled aggregates were used to reduce treatment costs and environmental burdens. Similarly, Sudagar et al. (2023) investigated low-grade Portuguese metakaolin, natural zeolite, and waste cork residue as replacements for commercial metakaolin-based geopolymers. The results showed that the applied waste-based polymers containing cork residue can effectively adsorb heavy metal cations such as Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺, Cu²⁺, and Zn²⁺ with a high level of selectivity. Masoumi and Ghaemi (2024) hypercrosslinked waste polycarbonate via Friedel-Crafts reaction to remove metallic ions from wastewater. In the investigation, the adsorption behavior of Pb²⁺ and Cd²⁺ ions was tested under varied conditions. Zennaki et al. (2023) investigated recycling waste-expanded polystyrene into anion exchange resins for Pb²⁺ and Cu²⁺ adsorption. Different modification techniques were examined to find the highest adsorption capacity and reusability. Radenković et al. (2024) explored using activated sunflower material (ASM) to remove Pb²⁺ and Cu²⁺ ions from wastewater. Optimal conditions were determined using Box-Behnken Design, with ASM showing high efficiency.

This study proposes reusing modified AAC waste, referred to as Low-Density Concrete (LDC), as an efficient adsorbent for removing Pb²⁺, Co²⁺, and Mn²⁺ from aquatic environments. LDC was characterized using X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF), Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR), Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET), X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis and Field Emission-Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM). Adsorption behavior was evaluated through isotherm modelling, adsorption kinetics using nonlinear Pseudo-First-Order (PFO) and Pseudo-Second-Order (PSO) models, and selectivity assessments under different concentration scenarios. The study further investigated competitive adsorption and morphological changes during the process. A Thales-based geometrical framework, the Adsorbent Regeneration Prediction Model (ARPM), is introduced for the first time to estimate regeneration cycles. The main objectives include implementing circular economy principles through construction waste reuse, demonstrating LDC characterization within Integrated Solid Waste Management (ISWM), determining adsorption mechanisms, and assessing regeneration potential. Key novelties are the simultaneous removal of three heavy metals using lightweight CDW, the development of ARPM to evaluate resiliency against pollution scenarios, and the integration of Sustainable Materials Management (SMM) with adsorption analysis.

It is important to note that the SMM concept has rarely been used to plan, track, and improve waste reduction with life-cycle-based metrics, as shown by Anshassi et al. (2019), or to support sustainable waste management through source reduction, material recovery, and energy recapture, as noted by Hall (2017). In this study, SMM is applied to select materials and assess the sustainability of an adsorbent. Also, the Thales' theorem-based model has not been used in this field before and is newly developed through this investigation. Qin et al. (2024) proposed simultaneous adsorption regeneration with sintered activated carbon based on kinetics modelling, and Yasri and Roberts (2024) outlined electrochemical regeneration concepts using mechanistic electrochemical modeling approach. However, their models remain physical and computationally complex for operators, while the ARPM introduced here simplifies calculations into a more practical and operator-friendly framework.

2. Materials and methods

The research roadmap of the present study is shown in Fig. 1. LDC waste was prepared and characterized by different tools in the first step. In the next step, the adsorption process of three heavy metals, including Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} , was optimized according to pH, mass of adsorbent, and contact time. In the third step, the isothermal behavior of LCD in the interaction of Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} was assessed based on eight different isotherm models, including Langmuir, Freundlich, Temkin, Dubinin-Radushkevich, Khan, Toth, Redlich-Peterson, and Sips. Furthermore, in the next phase of this study, the kinetics of heavy metal adsorption onto LDC was analyzed using PFO and PSO models. In addition, morphological changes were examined through elemental surface analysis before and after adsorption. The performance of LDC in heavy metal decontamination was also evaluated under competitive conditions to assess its selectivity and efficiency in multi-metal systems. Then, a Thales theorem-based model was presented to predict the regenerative adsorption cycle for each metal ion separately. Finally, the application of LDC waste material was assessed per the Sustainable Materials Management model.

2.1. Applied materials

A 1 g L^{-1} stock solution of Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} was purchased from Merck, Germany, for the experiments. Additionally, in some tests, the solutions were prepared using Lead(II) acetate trihydrate (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), Cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), and Manganese(II) sulfate monohydrate (Lach-Ner, Czech Republic). For pH adjustment of the solutions, HCl (0.1 mol L^{-1}) and NaOH (0.1 mol L^{-1}) from Merck, Germany are applied. Likewise, due to regeneration of the adsorbent, HNO_3 (1 mol L^{-1}), Merck, Germany was utilized.

2.2. LDC adsorbent preparation

The standard mixture consisted of Silica sand (350 $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), Water (305 $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), Cement Portland type II (25 $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), Lime (115 $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), and Aluminum powder (40 $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$). The LDC mixture was produced at Razavi Block Company in Mashhad, Iran, by mixing and casting the raw materials to achieve a density of 500 $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. The mixture was autoclaved at 101,325 Pa pressure and 150 °C for 3 h. After synthesis, the LDC was washed three times, dried, and crushed. The resulting materials were sieved through mesh No. 140 (0.105 mm) (He et al., 2025; Kang et al., 2025). During the production process of LDC, chemical reactions generated gases, which created micropores, macropores, and interstices in the LDC structure. This significantly increased its porosity and surface area (Qiao et al., 2008).

2.3. Characterization

To determine the chemical composition of the LDC adsorbent, XRF

(Philips PW 1480, Netherlands) was utilized. FTIR (Thermo Nicolet model AVATAR 370, USA) was used for the exact characterization of the chemical specification, with a concentration on qualitative identification of various organic and organic/metallic molecules, determination of the molecular structure of different species, and identification of functional groups in the structure of the adsorbent. Additionally, in some secondary FTIR analyses, spectra with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} were obtained using a germanium ATR crystal (NICOLET iZ10, Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), equipped with a horizontal ATR accessory featuring a single reflection angle of 45°.

The morphological evaluation of the adsorbent surface was conducted using a FE-SEM model Philips S360, manufactured by Oxford in the United Kingdom. Prior to imaging, the adsorbent surface was prepared by coating it with a thin layer of gold using a sputter coater. The imaging was performed under vacuum conditions at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV. The resulting images were analyzed using appropriate software (point electronic GmbH control software) to obtain information about the surface morphology, such as pores, cracks, and irregularities. Additionally, in some other tests, EDS and SEM analyses were performed using a Tescan Vega XMU SEM (TESCAN s.r.o., Brno, Czech Republic), which is equipped with Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) and elemental mapping capabilities. The specific surface area of the adsorbent was measured using the gas adsorption method (BET instrument Belsorp mini II, Japan). The XRD analysis of LDC was performed using a Rigaku MiniFlex 600 diffractometer with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$, operated at 40 kV and 30 mA), scanning from 10° to 70° with a step size of 0.01° per minute. Then, the results of the XRD analysis are evaluated using a program developed in MATLAB 2019b as part of this research.

2.4. Experimental practices and study of the effect of operational condition

The pH of a solution is a critical factor in removing ions from aqueous solutions. It affects the surface charge of the adsorbent and the degree of ionization and speciation of heavy metals in the solution (Yan et al., 2016). To prevent the precipitation of heavy metal ions, we studied the effect of pH on cation removal in the acidic pH range of 2.0 to 5.0, where the studied heavy metals are present in a cationic form (Harris, 2010).

The experimental set-up was a batch system to assess LDC performance in heavy metal adsorption. The fixed amount of sorbent (6.67 g L^{-1}) was added to 15 ml of metal solution at a concentration of 10 mg L^{-1} (with a dilution of 1 g L^{-1} stock solution of metal ions). The concentration was determined based on the study by Martemianov et al. (2017) and reflects levels that may be present in certain water sources, such as fish farms (Olaifa et al., 2003). The pH and temperature were fixed at 5.0 ± 0.1 (Metrohm 827 pH, Switzerland) and $25 \text{ °C} \pm 0.1$, respectively. The effect of contact time was evaluated between 0–120 min with 400 rpm stirring using the one-factor-at-a-time (OFAT) method. Next, the optimal amount of adsorbent (LDC) was examined in the 0.02–0.15 g range.

Fig. 1. The research roadmap of the present study.

After a selected contact time, separation was performed by centrifuging at 3000 rpm for 10 min (Andreas Hettich D72, Tuttlingen, Germany). For heavy metal pollution detection, AAS was used (Perkin Elmer AAnalyst 700 Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy with specific lamps for each metal Pb: 283.3 nm, Co: 240.7 nm, and Mn: 279.5 nm) according to Farrukh (2012) and Loon (2012). Furthermore, in the kinetics and competitive adsorption tests, heavy metal concentrations were measured using ICP-OES (Thermo Scientific, USA).

2.5. Adsorption isotherms and regeneration cycles

Two-parameter isothermal models, including Freundlich and Langmuir, were initially employed to evaluate the isothermal behavior of LDC for each heavy metal. Langmuir is a monolayer adsorption isotherm that limits the adsorption to a single molecular layer. According to this model, increasing the distance from the adsorbent surface significantly reduces the intermolecular forces (Foo and Hameed, 2010). Freundlich adsorption isotherm is an empirical equation and one of the most practical approaches to analyzing adsorption (Foo and Hameed, 2010). This method is more suitable for evaluating adsorption on heterogeneous surfaces, mainly when dealing with low to moderate concentrations. However, due to the close coefficient of determination in the mentioned models, three-parameter techniques, such as Khan, Toth, Redlich-Peterson, and Sips, were utilized. Finally, a combination of these models was used to determine the adsorption mechanism for each heavy metal. All equations and models applied in this part of the research are summarized in Table S1. Comparably, two-parameter models such as the Temkin and Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherms are used to accurately determine the principles of adsorption in a variety of physical, intra-particle diffusion, or chemical classifications (Gheibi et al., 2022).

In this study, the regenerability of the adsorbent is evaluated over five cycles. During each adsorption-desorption cycle, 1 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ is used to regenerate heavy metal ions from the adsorbent surface. The regeneration performance is assessed based on the optimal interaction of the adsorbent with the heavy metal ions and in industrial concentration of the heavy metals.

2.6. Kinetics analysis

In the present study, kinetic analyses were conducted under controlled conditions: pH = 5 and adsorbent dosage = 3.34 g L⁻¹. The reaction was monitored over a time range of 0–120 min, with a fixed reactor volume of 30 mL. Also, the initial concentration of heavy metals in the solution is adjusted around 5 mg L⁻¹. The experimental data were evaluated using two kinetic models: pseudo-first-order (PFO) and pseudo-second-order (PSO) (Table S2) (Wang and Guo, 2020). The performance of each model was assessed based on the coefficient of determination (R²) and the differences between the experimental and theoretical adsorption capacities.

2.7. Morphology changes analysis

To better understand the reaction mechanism, morphological changes in the LDC surface were evaluated before and after adsorption using SEM and EDS characterization. The objective of this analysis was to detect the presence of Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, and Pb²⁺ on the LDC surface. The adsorption experiments were conducted under controlled conditions: pH = 5, contact time = 30 min, adsorbent dosage = 3.34 g L⁻¹, solution volume = 30 mL, and metal ion concentrations of approximately 5 mg L⁻¹.

2.8. Competitive adsorption

To further understand the selectivity of the adsorbent, competitive adsorption tests among Pb²⁺, Co²⁺, and Mn²⁺ were conducted. The

experiments were performed under controlled conditions: pH = 5, contact time = 30 minutes, adsorbent dosage = 3.34 g L⁻¹, and solution volume = 30 mL. The competitive behavior was evaluated across three concentration scenarios: low, medium, and high. In each scenario, the metal ion with the highest affinity toward LDC was considered the primary adsorbate, while the other two acted as interfering ions.

2.9. Adsorbent regeneration prediction model (ARPM)

This research introduces the ARPM based on Thales' Theorem (Grecu et al., 2020), for predicting adsorbent performance in various cycles of water and wastewater treatment processes. In this new method, the trend of removal percentage in repeated adsorption cycles is evaluated with the geometrical Thales Theorem. Consideration of effective parameters including the number of cycles (N), initial concentration (C₀), remaining concentration in first adsorption cycle (C_{Ri}), remained concentration in last adsorption cycle (C_{Rn}) and allowable standard concentration of the metal ion in water resources (C_s), the number of cycle reaction that can meet standard thresholds are estimated. According to Fig. 2, reducing heavy metal removal percentage in different cycles is considered as a triangle, and Thales geometrical rules (Eq. (1)) are applied to it. In the mentioned equation Δ_i expresses the difference between the removal percentage in the first cycle and the removal percentage in the standard concentration threshold (considering allowable standard concentration) and, Δ_n express the difference of removal percentage in first and last cycles.

$$\frac{\Delta_i}{\Delta_n} = \frac{x}{N} \quad (1)$$

After simplifying Eq. (1) with fundamental definition of the parameters, the final mathematical model for determining the LDC regeneration cycle (N-x) is expressed in Eq. (2). In other words, after calculating the x-factor, the adsorbent should be regenerated to meet the standard of heavy metals in water resources.

$$x = N \times \frac{C_{Rn} - C_s}{C_{Rn} - C_{Ri}} \rightarrow N - x = N \times \left(1 - \frac{C_{Rn} - C_s}{C_{Rn} - C_{Ri}}\right) \quad (2)$$

The application of this model is valid only when the standard concentration lies within the range of concentrations being evaluated. In other words, the initial concentration must progressively decrease to meet the standard limits of the receiving water body over successive adsorption cycles. In this type of equation, the linearity condition of efficiency reduction across different adsorption cycles is first satisfied, followed by the triangulation required for the application of Thales' theorem.

Fig. 2. Scheme of Thales-based ARPM in this research.

Through mathematical modeling, it becomes possible to determine the regeneration cycle of LDC adsorbent when dealing with unknown water or wastewater samples. In this study, the regeneration cycle is illustrated using the influent heavy metal content (Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+}) data from a wastewater treatment plant located in the Toos Industrial Park of Mashhad City, Iran. Additionally, Cs values conforming to WHO standards in river water are incorporated into the formula (Rozana et al., 2020; Waghmare et al., 2015). However, it is essential to note that regeneration tests are conducted individually for each metal ion under optimal conditions for heavy metals.

2.10. Sustainable materials management models

In this section of study, the applied concrete-based material as an adsorbent is analyzed based on Sustainable Materials Management (SMM) prioritization tools which was introduced by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), USA (US EPA, 2020). The lifecycle-based Sustainable Materials Management Prioritization Tools provide a basis for spotting chances to improve environmental sustainability in the creation and consumption of goods and services. They identify critical

environmental issues and hotspots, which helps with action prioritization and efficient resource allocation. More thorough information should be added to these tools to make exact decisions prior to taking action (Chen et al., 2017).

EPA's sustainability assessment uses a life-cycle-based analytic framework incorporating tools like Comprehensive Environmental Data Archive (CEDA 3.0) and U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis 1998 input/output (BEA I/O) tables to evaluate 480 materials, products, and services across 17 criteria, including environmental impacts (e.g., toxicity, GWP), resource use, and waste. Impacts are assessed from direct, intermediate, and final consumption perspectives. A vector analysis method is applied to compute relative rankings and guide sustainability prioritization strategies (US EPA, 2015). The SMM prioritization framework applies life-cycle input-output (LCA-IO) modeling where economic activity vectors are multiplied by environmental extension coefficients. Using the Leontief inverse $(I - A)^{-1}$, total upstream requirements are derived. Indicators span environmental, resource, waste, and socio-economic. Computation involves normalizing impacts across categories and applying vector magnitude analysis to generate comparative sustainability scores (US EPA, 2015).

Fig. 3. The outputs of LDC adsorbent characterization based on (a) FT-IR spectrum, (b) XRF analysis, (c) FE-SEM, scale bar: 500 nm, and (d) FE-SEM, scale bar: 200 nm images.

The present study applied a concrete-based material for the decontamination of heavy metals (Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+}). While the application of carbon and graphite materials (such as Graphene Oxide-GO) are common for the decontamination of heavy metals from water resources (Li et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2011; Yan et al., 2014). Therefore, in this part of study, the sustainability indexes of both (1) concrete-based and (2) carbon/graphite-based materials are analyzed. The SMM analysis is done in five different categorizations summarized in Table S3 (US EPA, 2020).

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Characterization of adsorbent

The FTIR spectrum characterization is presented in Fig. 3a. The symmetric stretching of Si-O can be detected at 973 cm^{-1} . In addition, a weaker feature was observed around 672 cm^{-1} . The Si-O rocking vibration band can also be observed at 453 cm^{-1} , based on the FTIR results (Herth et al., 2016; Liang et al., 2012). CO_3^{2-} bands are present at 882 cm^{-1} (out-of-plane bend), and the asymmetric stretching signal of calcite/aragonite is demonstrated at 1431 cm^{-1} . The broad band at 3446 cm^{-1} is primarily related to O—H stretching vibration due to adsorbed water in the sample (Bergren et al., 1978).

To characterize the chemical composition of the LDC adsorbent, X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis was performed on the LDC samples (Fig. 3b). There were six oxides determined, with a majority of Al_2O_3 and CaO. The sum of measured chemical composition is not equal to 100 %, which indicates the presence of adsorbed water and carbonate compounds (Beckhoff et al., 2007). FE-SEM images of the LDC adsorbent (Fig. 3c,d) shows a high porosity that might cause a high affinity for the adsorption of heavy metals. Numerous investigations have demonstrated that adding aluminum powder to concrete increases its porosity (Van et al., 2019). Hydrogen gas is produced by the reaction between the aluminum powder and the calcium hydroxide in the concrete mixture as it cures. Additionally, during adsorption, this reaction increases the specific surface area and adsorption process efficiency. The specific surface area of LDC was determined to be $30.2\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$, based on the N_2 adsorption isotherms measured by BET analysis. This is in a range of various CDW materials that are applied for adsorption process of contaminations, e.g., calcinated AAC (Gheibi et al., 2022), lightweight cellular concrete (Azizi et al., 2023), and ultra-lightweight concrete (Yu et al., 2015) have the surface areas of $24.64\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$, $12.86\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$, and $50\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$, respectively.

3.2. Study the effect of pH on adsorption

The result of studying the effect of pH on adsorption is shown in Fig. 4a. The poor adsorption at low pH is due to the protonation of adsorption sites, resulting in a net positive charge on the surface (Xu, 2013). The observed difference in the removal rate of different metal

ions at low pH can be attributed to the varying binding between the adsorbent functional groups and metal ions, depending on the charges of the metal ions and the specific characteristics of the adsorbent surface (Mathialagan and Viraraghavan, 2002). As it is clear from Fig. 4a, the maximum removal (%) can be seen at the maximal pH considered in the experiment, $\text{pH}=5.0$, for all three ions.

Based on the solubility product constant (K_{sp}) in the dissolution of metal ions in water samples, precipitation can occur for Pb^{2+} ($K_{\text{sp}}=8 \times 10^{-16}$), Co^{2+} ($K_{\text{sp}}=1.3 \times 10^{-15}$), and Mn^{2+} ($K_{\text{sp}}=1.6 \times 10^{-13}$) (Harris, 2010) at pH levels of ~ 7.5 , 7.79 , and 8.82 respectively, with a concentration of 200 mg L^{-1} of heavy metals in the reactor. 200 mg L^{-1} was the maximum concentration of heavy metals which is applied and therefore, for other concentrations, the pH of precipitation will be higher than the above-written values (Harris, 2010). Thus, this study aims to evaluate the pure adsorption process for all selected metal ions within the same environment, thus, pH 5 can be considered the ultimate value in the assessment.

The chemistry of the heavy metal ions and the metal oxide adsorbent materials (such as SiO_2 , CaO, and Al_2O_3) can both explain the phenomenon, which indicates that the removal percentage of heavy metals in adsorption processes is lower at more acidic pH ($\text{pH}=2$). The major metal oxides present have a net positive charge on their surfaces at low pH. For example, SiO_2 's surface tends to be positively charged at low pH levels because protonated silanol groups (Si-OH^+) are present (Brown et al., 2014; Ho and McKay, 1999; Lagergren, 1907).

Pb^{2+} showed higher adsorption at pH 2 than Co^{2+} , and Co^{2+} higher than Mn^{2+} . This is because Pb^{2+} attaches to the adsorbent surface more readily than Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} because of their more positive charge (Xu, 2013) and could make surface complexes more easily than Co^{2+} or Mn^{2+} (Dzombak and Morel, 1991; Sparks et al., 2022; Stumm and Morgan, 2013).

3.3. Optimum contact time and doses of LDC

As shown in Fig. 4b, it can be understood that the optimum contact time for both Co^{2+} and Pb^{2+} is 20 min. After this time, the Removal Percentage (RP) for heavy metals reached 98 % for Pb^{2+} and 80 % for Co^{2+} . During the 120-minute kinetic experiments, there was only a negligible change in RP, around 1 % for Pb^{2+} and around 4 % for Co^{2+} . Therefore, 20 min can be considered the optimal contact time for the adsorption of these ions, whereas for Mn^{2+} , 30 min is identified as the optimal reaction time.

The behavior of adsorbents toward heavy metals varies. However, in this study, the minimal contact time to get equilibrium adsorption was found to be between 20 and 30 min (Co^{2+} and Pb^{2+} : 20 min, Mn^{2+} : 30 min). Panda et al. (2020) demonstrated that significant removal of metal ions (over 80 %) occurred in 0–20 min of contact time when various heavy metals were adsorbed onto geopolymer made from dolochar ash. The fastest adsorption in the first phase of the test is attributed to the presence of numerous binding sites on the surface of dolochar ash

Fig. 4. Heavy metals removal as a function of (a) pH, (b) time, and (c) LDC dosage, general conditions: 10 mg L^{-1} of each heavy metal, $\text{pH}=5$, 6.67 g L^{-1} of LDC powder, 30 min contact time. Repeatability error for Pb^{2+} : less than 1%, Mn^{2+} : 7%, and Co^{2+} : 4.3%.

geopolymer. Similar trends in adsorption efficiency have been observed (Siyal et al., 2016), where saturation of adsorption of heavy metal ions on potent adsorbents like fly ash, coal, and geopolymeric Linz-Donawitz (LD) slag typically occurs within 30–60 min (Elimbi et al., 2011; Sarkar et al., 2017). Senberber et al. (2017) demonstrated that in the application of borax sludge for decontamination of chromium ions, maximum performance can be achieved in less than 30 min. Likewise, Bulut and Tez (2007) proved that in the adsorption of heavy metals by sawdust as a waste material, maximum adsorption can be observed in less than 30 min of the reaction.

The adsorption mechanism of Pb^{2+} and Zn^{2+} using slaked lime ($Ca(OH)_2$) is based on the precipitation of metal hydroxides. Lime dissolves to form Ca^{2+} and $2OH^-$ ions, which react with metal ions in water. Pb^{2+} and Zn^{2+} form $Pb(OH)_2$ and $Zn(OH)_2$, respectively, as precipitates. The efficiency depends on maintaining an optimal pH range. High alkalinity from lime can cause re-dissolution of amphoteric hydroxides, reducing removal efficiency (Wang et al., 2016). Harja et al. (2017) demonstrated that the adsorption of Pb^{2+} onto lime-based adsorbent reached its maximum within 50–60 min. Consequently, the evaluated LDC exhibited synergistic effects, including the influence of the CaO compound, which enhanced the kinetic behavior. Pb^{2+} sorption on $\gamma-Al_2O_3$ involves a rapid initial adsorption phase followed by a slower phase, consistent with an inner-sphere bidentate bonding mechanism. The rapid phase, which accounts for 76 % of total Pb^{2+} adsorption within 15 min, involves Pb binding to surface aluminol groups (Strawn et al., 1998). Therefore, in the present study, the rapid adsorption of heavy metals can be attributed to the presence of aluminum powder in the adsorbent mixture. In another study, Tabesh et al. (2018) demonstrated that the adsorption of Pb^{2+} and Cd^{2+} onto $\gamma-Al_2O_3$ nanoparticles resulted in the elimination of over 80 % of the contaminants within the first 10 min. In contrast, in the present study, around 5 % of the concrete weight consists of aluminum oxide, which provides an additional driving force in the LDC reaction, enhancing the kinetic performance of the adsorption process.

According to Fig. 4c, it is evident that an adsorbent amount of 6.67 g L^{-1} in the reactors yields sufficient results. In the case of Pb^{2+} , the RP value remains unchanged between 0.1 g and 0.15 g (6.67–10 g L^{-1}), and for Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} , the changes were only 1.17 % and 1.75 %, respectively. Therefore, 0.1 g (6.67 g L^{-1}) of LDC mass versus RP is sufficient, indicating its optimal value.

In the present investigation, the choice of 0.105 mm particle size was made to highlight the effect of size on adsorption performance. Smaller particles generally enhance adsorption due to their higher surface area and shorter diffusion pathways, which accelerate ion transfer and increase active site accessibility (Suresh Kumar et al., 2019). However, very fine particles often lead to suspension stability issues and hinder solid–liquid separation. Conversely, larger particles settle easily but reduce adsorption kinetics because of limited surface exposure (Sharma, 2018). The selected size provided a balance between high adsorption efficiency and practical handling, ensuring good reactivity while avoiding excessive colloidal behavior.

3.4. Adsorption studies

The experimental data determined for all three heavy metals were fitted with all types of considered isotherms (two and three parameters) with the aim of understanding the mechanisms of the adsorption process.

3.4.1. Two parameter isotherms

3.4.1.1. Langmuir isotherm. The data can be easily fit with the Langmuir adsorption isotherm with a high R^2 equal to 0.97, 0.93 and 0.89 for Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} adsorption, respectively (Table 1). Therefore, the correlation of the Langmuir isotherm for Pb^{2+} is greater than for the

Table 1

Results of the study of two-parameter isotherms.

Two Parameter Isotherm	Parameter	Co^{2+}	Pb^{2+}	Mn^{2+}
Langmuir	Q_{max} (mg g^{-1})	15.17	43.1	23.52
	K_{ads} (L mg^{-1})	0.0326	2.86	0.0115
	R^2	0.93	0.97	0.89
Freundlich	$1/n$	0.525	0.703	1.01
	K_F (mg g^{-1})	1.05	40.43	0.32
	R^2	0.98	0.99	0.99
Temkin	K_T (L mg^{-1})	0.82	77.3	0.26
	b (J mol^{-1})	1027.53	389.9	675.7
	R^2	0.88	0.88	0.96
D-R	Q_m (mg g^{-1})	7.88	24.92	8.54
	K (mol^2 kJ^{-2})	1E-6	2E-8	8E-06
	E (J mol^{-1})	707.1	5000	250
	R^2	0.82	0.96	0.89

others. The Langmuir model assumes that adsorption occurs in a monolayer and only at specific, fixed sites that are identical in energy and equivalent (Foo and Hameed, 2010). There are no interactions or hindrances between adjacent molecules on these sites. Furthermore, Langmuir's theory associates a rapid decrease in intermolecular attractive forces with increasing distance (Foo and Hameed, 2010). Therefore, the Langmuir isotherm assumes uniform adsorption, where each molecule has constant enthalpies and sorption activation energy, and all sites have equal affinity for the adsorbate. Additionally, there is no movement of the adsorbate across the surface (Radenković et al., 2024). Graphically, Langmuir adsorption model is represented by a curve with a plateau, indicating saturation where increasing solute concentration does not cause further adsorption because all adsorption sites are occupied.

When comparing the heavy metal, it should be mentioned that Langmuir adsorption capacity (Q_{max}) is highest for Pb^{2+} (43.1 $mg\ g^{-1}$) > Mn^{2+} (23.52 $mg\ g^{-1}$) > Co^{2+} (15.17 $mg\ g^{-1}$). Therefore, the strength of adsorption of Pb^{2+} with LDC was more than that of Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} . In this study, the hydrated radius of Pb^{2+} (4.01 Å) is smaller than that of Mn^{2+} (4.38 Å) and Co^{2+} (4.23 Å). Therefore, the hydration of Pb^{2+} by water molecules will be lower compared to the other two ions. Consequently, the unoccupied active sites of Pb^{2+} can participate more readily in adsorption stages with LDC compared to Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} . This could be a contributing factor to the higher adsorption capacity of Pb^{2+} compared to Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} (Goel et al., 2004).

A dimensionless constant, referred to as the separation factor (R_L) defined by Webber and Chakravorti, can be expressed as Eq. (3) (Weber and Chakravorti, 1974).

$$R_L = \frac{1}{K_{ads}C_0 + 1} \quad (3)$$

where K_{ads} and C_0 represent the Langmuir constant ($L\ mg^{-1}$) and initial concentration of contamination ($mg\ L^{-1}$), respectively. The computations demonstrated that the R_L for Pb^{2+} for all concentrations between 10–200 $mg\ L^{-1}$ has a value between 0.03 to 0.001 values. Therefore, the $0 < R_L < 1$ and it is a favorable adsorption process. Also, the R_L has value between 0.3 to 0.9 for the same concentrations of Mn^{2+} . While in 10 $mg\ L^{-1}$ concentration of Mn^{2+} , the R_L is near to 1 and it means that at a lower initial concentrations, the adsorption process will be done linearly ($R_L=1$). Finally, in the case of Co^{2+} , the $0.1 < R_L < 0.75$ and therefore, the process of adsorption is favorable like to Pb^{2+} one (Foo and Hameed, 2010). The curve-fitting results of the Langmuir isotherm model for all applied metal ions are represented in Fig. S1a.

3.4.1.2. Freundlich isotherm. The second isotherm tested was Freundlich. The Freundlich isotherm suggests multilayer adsorption on heterogeneous surfaces. It indicates that adsorption capacity increases as concentration rises, with multiple adsorption layers forming at different energy levels (Foo and Hameed, 2010; Ramadan and El-Masry, 2024).

Assessing whether the measured data conforms to the Freundlich isotherm can best be done by displaying them on a log-log scale. While the data for Co^{2+} can be fitted by a straight line, the data for the other two metals show a decrease in the adsorbed amount for the highest concentration in solution. This shows saturation of sorption and therefore, in the case of Pb^{2+} and Mn^{2+} the data were plotted as a straight line without the point corresponding to the highest concentration. Then the best fit of all applied metallic ions to the Freundlich model was over 0.98 (Table 1) and the Freundlich isotherm is valid up to 120 mg L^{-1} for Co^{2+} , 40 mg L^{-1} for Mn^{2+} , and 0.2 mg L^{-1} for Pb^{2+} .

The analysis of the model confirmed that the adsorption processes of Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} onto LCD wastes occur with multilayer adsorption and on heterogeneous surfaces. However, the results of Pb^{2+} adsorption were fitted to both Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms. Therefore, understanding heterogeneous or homogeneous surfaces is not straightforward and should be further discussed with the analysis of three-parameter models (Khan, Toth, Redlich-Peterson, and Sips). In total, the Freundlich constant of Pb^{2+} equal to 40.43 mg g^{-1} was considerably higher than both Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} . Consequently, the flux of the lead adsorption process exceeded that of the other two metals in the mass transfer process of adsorption. Additionally, in the lead adsorption process, the $1/n$ value was lower than that of the other two metals, indicating cooperative procedure (Haghsheresht and Lu, 1998) in the lead adsorption onto LDC waste compared to Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} . The results of curve fitting in the Freundlich model are demonstrated in Fig. S1b.

3.4.1.3. Temkin isotherm. According to Table 1 and Fig. S1c, it is evident that the adsorption of Mn^{2+} ions onto LDC wastes followed the Temkin isotherm model more closely than Pb^{2+} and Co^{2+} . The R^2 coefficient for Mn^{2+} was ~ 0.96 , while for both Pb^{2+} and Co^{2+} it was ~ 0.88 . The Temkin isotherm includes a factor that explicitly considers adsorbent-adsorbate interactions. By disregarding extremely low and high concentrations, the model assumes that the heat of adsorption (which is dependent on temperature) of all molecules in the layer would decrease linearly rather than logarithmically with coverage. As shown in the equation (Table S1), its derivation assumes a uniform distribution of binding energies, up to a certain maximum binding energy (Kim et al., 2004). Consideration to Table 1, it is clear that b value for all ions was less than 8 kJ mol^{-1} and therefore, the adsorption of Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} were carried out physically onto LDC wastes. However, the certainty of this result for Mn^{2+} is greater than two others because of its coefficient of determination values, which will be evaluated more in D-R isotherm assessment.

3.4.1.4. Dubinin-Radushkevich (D-R) isotherm. D-R isotherm parameters for each metal are given in Table 1 and Fig. S1d. Considering $R^2 > 0.96$, only Pb^{2+} follows the D-R isotherm. Besides, all values obtained for parameter E from Table 1 are less than 8 kJ mol^{-1} (Demiral and Güngör, 2016), which indicates the physical nature of the adsorption process for all metals. Results obtained from the E parameter verify all conclusions received from the b parameter in the Temkin isotherm model about the nature of the adsorption, which is physical.

3.4.2. Three parameter isotherms

All the R^2 values for studied heavy metals according to 3-parameter isotherms are higher than 0.94, indicating the high versatility of heavy metals adsorption onto LDC adsorbent according to this model.

3.4.2.1. Khan isotherm model. The Khan isotherm is a generalized model proposed for pure solutions, where a_k and b_k represent the model exponent and model constant, respectively. With relatively high correlation coefficients and minimum sum square error or chi-square values, it is possible to accurately determine its maximum uptake values (Khan et al., 1997). The coefficient of determination of Khan isotherm for Co^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} is more than 0.98 (Table 2 and Fig. S1e). However, it

Table 2

Results of the study of three-parameter isotherms.

Three Parameter Isotherm	Parameter	Co^{2+}	Pb^{2+}	Mn^{2+}
Khan	q_s	5168.53	15.42	11,203.43
	b_k	5.63E-5	8.25	2.67E-5
	a_k	154.71	0.59	318.29
	R^2	0.98	0.99	0.99
Toth	K_{Toth}	0.43	6.98	0.83
	a_T	0.13	0.01	0.77
	t	1.95	2.49	2.29
	R^2	0.96	0.99	0.94
Sips	K_S	73.88	0.06	0.05
	a_S	1.2	0.004	0.004
	β_S	0.85	1.6	1.6
	R^2	0.97	0.99	0.99
R-P	K_R	0.22	73.13	0.23
	a_R	9.17E-6	30.72	2.24E-7
	g	2.46	12.81	3.24
	R^2	0.98	0.99	0.99

should be noted that a_k value does not converge to 1 for each metallic ion adsorption onto LDC waste, indicating that the adsorption process is not Langmuir. Consequently, it can be understood that with the application of a three-parameter adsorption process, the heterogeneous surface of the reaction is evident. In the following section, the accuracy of this claim will be analyzed using three other parameter isothermal models.

3.4.2.2. Toth isotherm model. The Toth isotherm model is an additional empirical equation designed to improve Langmuir isotherm fittings using experimental data. It is particularly effective in describing heterogeneous adsorption systems, as it satisfies both low and high-end concentration boundaries. This model assumes an asymmetric quasi-Gaussian energy distribution, where most sites have adsorption energies lower than the peak (maximum) or mean value (Ho et al., 2002). According to Table 2 and Fig. S1f, it is evident that the adsorption of Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Co^{2+} follows the Toth model with a R^2 of more than ~ 0.94 . However, upon calculation, it becomes clear that the $1/t$ values for all metallic ions are around 0.5, significantly different from 1. Therefore, this three-parameter isothermal model supports Khan's assertion, confirming the heterogeneous surface of adsorption onto LDC wastes once again.

3.4.2.3. Sips isotherm model. The values of the Sips isotherm parameters for this study are presented in Table 2. According to the model, it can be understood that all metallic ion adsorption processes onto LDC waste have been fitted to Sips model with at least 0.97 correlation coefficient. Based on the B_S parameter values in Table 2 and the curve fitting results shown in Fig. S1g, it can be observed that under Sips isotherm conditions, B_S does not converge to 1. Consequently, it does not follow the Langmuir isotherm, indicating that the adsorption process for Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Co^{2+} occurred on a heterogeneous surface, consistent with the findings of the Khan and Toth model.

3.4.2.4. Redlich-Peterson (R-P) isotherm model. The R-P model values for this research are listed in Table 2 and Fig. S1h. The values of g parameter for Pb^{2+} ($R^2 = 0.99$), Co^{2+} ($R^2 = 0.98$) and Mn^{2+} ($R^2 = 0.99$) metals are not close to 1 and therefore, the model's outcomes proved the heterogeneous surface of reaction. Finally, all two and three parameter isothermal equations determined the multilayer adsorption of the ions onto the adsorbent.

As a summary, various isotherm models were applied to fit the adsorption data in this study. The results from two-parameter models (Langmuir and Freundlich) and three-parameter models (Khan, Toth, Sips, and Redlich-Peterson) indicate that the adsorption occurs in multiple layers and the LDC surface is heterogeneous. Additionally, the Temkin and Dubinin-Radushkevich models prove that the adsorption of

Pb²⁺, Co²⁺, and Mn²⁺ onto LDC is dominated by physisorption.

According to Al-Maliky et al. (2021), concrete-based adsorbents possess a high point of zero charge (PZC) of ~12, meaning their surfaces are positively charged below this value and negatively charged above it, which dictates the adsorption pathway: favoring anions under acidic conditions and cations under alkaline ones. However, in LDC tested at pH 2–5, far below the ZPC, heavy metals such as Pb²⁺, Mn²⁺, and Co²⁺ were still efficiently removed, not by electrostatic attraction but through ion exchange with Ca²⁺ and Al³⁺ and complexation with surface hydroxyls. Adsorption capacities followed the trend Pb²⁺ (43.1 mg/g) > Mn²⁺ (23.5 mg/g) > Co²⁺ (15.2 mg/g), consistent with ionic size and binding affinity, with Pb²⁺ showing the strongest uptake. Thus, while concrete's surface charge condition governs adsorption behavior, LDC demonstrates that below-ZPC environments still enable effective cation removal through chemical interactions, emphasizing its sustainable potential in heavy metal remediation.

3.5. Kinetics analysis of heavy metal adsorption

The nonlinear kinetic modeling (Ait Ichou et al., 2023; Canzano et al., 2012) outcomes (Table 3 and Figs. S2–S4) clearly indicate that the PSO model provides a superior description of adsorption kinetics compared to the PFO model for all three metal ions. This indicates that the adsorption rate may be influenced by the concentration of both the metal ions and the available active sites on the adsorbent surface (Wang and Guo, 2020). For Pb²⁺, the PFO fit yielded an R² of 0.69, RMSE of 0.065, and MAE of 0.05, while the PSO fit improved drastically with R² = 0.97, RMSE = 0.019, and MAE = 0.017. The theoretical q_e predicted by the PSO model (1.28 mg g⁻¹) was also closer to the experimental value than that of the PFO model (1.26 mg g⁻¹), suggesting that Pb²⁺ adsorption onto LDC is best explained by surface-controlled adsorption pathways. For Co²⁺, although PFO achieved a relatively high R² of 0.89, the PSO model again showed better agreement (R² = 0.90) while reducing MAE from 0.11 to 0.10 and improving q_e prediction from 1.55 mg g⁻¹ (PFO) to 1.72 mg g⁻¹ (PSO). Mn²⁺ adsorption followed the same pattern, with the PFO model giving R² = 0.51, RMSE = 0.15, and MAE = 0.11, whereas the PSO model improved these metrics to R² = 0.76, RMSE = 0.10, and MAE = 0.08, with q_e = 1.07 mg g⁻¹. Collectively, these numerical values demonstrate that PSO consistently provides a better statistical and predictive fit than PFO.

The figures provide analytical support for these statistical results. In Fig. S2 (Pb²⁺), the kinetic model comparison shows that the PSO curve overlaps almost entirely with the experimental data, whereas PFO underestimates adsorption at equilibrium. The residuals plot shows PSO residuals distributed narrowly within ±0.02 mg g⁻¹, compared to PFO which shows deviations up to 0.15 mg g⁻¹. The parity plot shows PSO points clustering tightly along the y = x line, while PFO deviates, especially at higher q_e values. Similarly, in Fig. S3 (Co²⁺) and Fig. S4 (Mn²⁺), the PFO model exhibits greater fluctuations compared to the

Table 3

The outcomes of kinetics models for three different types of heavy metal adsorption in this study. Condition: pH = 5, Time = 0–120 min, V = 30 mL, Mass of adsorbent = 3.34 g L⁻¹, Pb²⁺-C₀ = 4.15 mg L⁻¹, Co²⁺-C₀ = 5.79 mg L⁻¹, and Mn²⁺-C₀ = 5.52 mg L⁻¹. Pb²⁺: STD_{ave} = 0.22, Co²⁺: STD_{ave} = 0.22, and Mn²⁺: STD_{ave} = 0.31, the number of replications = 2.

PFO model	R ²	RMSE	MAE	k ₁ (min ⁻¹)	Theoretical q _e (mg g ⁻¹)
Pb ²⁺	0.69	0.065	0.05	1	1.26
Co ²⁺	0.89	0.14	0.11	0.095	1.55
Mn ²⁺	0.51	0.15	0.11	0.25	1.02
PSO model	R ²			k ₂ (g·mg ⁻¹ ·min ⁻¹)	Theoretical q _e (mg g ⁻¹)
Pb ²⁺	0.97	0.019	0.017	1.99	1.28
Co ²⁺	0.90	0.14	0.1	0.076	1.72
Mn ²⁺	0.76	0.1	0.08	0.49	1.07

PSO model, as reflected by the wider distribution of residual values. These numerical reductions in residual ranges confirm that PSO reduces both random and systematic deviations from experimental kinetics.

These improvements quantitatively demonstrate that the adsorption kinetics follow a PSO mechanism, indicative surface complexation dominated by electron exchange or sharing. Pb²⁺ exhibits the most pronounced strong surface binding behavior with near-perfect PSO fitting, Co²⁺ shows moderate but consistent PSO superiority, and Mn²⁺ presents weaker but still statistically significant improvement. This tiered performance suggests different binding strengths and mechanisms among the ions, with Pb²⁺ having the strongest affinity toward LDC surfaces.

The result suggests a stronger interaction or faster uptake of Pb²⁺ by the adsorbent, potentially due to its physicochemical properties such as hydration energy or ionic radius (Conway and Ayranci, 1999). Fig. S2-S4 illustrates this trend through the steeper slope observed for Pb²⁺ uptake over time. As a result, the findings highlight that the PSO model provides a more accurate and reliable description of the adsorption kinetics for all three metal ions, with Pb²⁺ exhibiting the highest rate constant and most rapid adsorption behavior under the studied conditions.

3.6. Morphology changes in the adsorption process

SEM images, EDS spectra, and elemental mapping are included in Fig. 5(a–d), which shows the morphological and elemental analysis of LDC both before and after heavy metal adsorption. The surface of virgin LDC has a rough, porous, and heterogeneously layered morphology, as seen in Fig. 5a. BET analysis confirmed that the LDC adsorbent possesses a specific surface area of 30.2 m² g⁻¹, and FE-SEM imaging revealed a porous morphology with numerous micro- and macropores. Together, these characterizations demonstrate that the structure provides a considerable surface area and abundant active sites, which are advantageous for adsorption. In accordance with the anticipated composition of the material, the related EDS spectrum verifies the presence of native elements such as oxygen (35.7 wt. %), silicon (19.3 wt. %), calcium (34.2 wt. %), and aluminum (2.1 wt. %). These elements are evenly distributed throughout the surface, as seen in the elemental mapping images.

Upon exposure to Pb²⁺ ions, as seen in Fig. 5b, the LDC surface becomes slightly more compact, likely due to the deposition or complexation of Pb species. The EDS analysis reveals the appearance of a small Pb signal, quantified at approximately 0.1 wt. %, indicating significant adsorption. A slight reduction in Ca and Mg levels suggests potential ion exchange mechanisms. Elemental mapping confirms the homogeneous dispersion of Pb throughout the LDC matrix, particularly in regions also rich in Mg, implying multivalent interactions with surface sites.

Fig. 5c displays the morphological and elemental characteristics of LDC after Co²⁺ adsorption. The SEM image reveals minor surface roughening and possible aggregation, while the EDS data confirm Co presence at 0.2 wt. %. There is also a modest decline in native elements such as Mg and Al, again supporting the likelihood of surface exchange or coordination. Co is distributed uniformly across the surface in the mapping images, which suggests effective and stable interaction of Co²⁺ ions with the LDC framework. Likewise, in Fig. 5(d), following Mn²⁺ adsorption, the LDC retains its overall surface structure but shows minor densification and particle boundary smoothing. The EDS spectrum verifies the presence of Mn at 0.6 wt. %, with little change in other major elemental concentrations. The elemental maps display a consistent Mn distribution, reinforcing the reproducibility and effectiveness of adsorption under these conditions.

Fig. 6 displays the FTIR spectra of LDC before adsorption (black line) and after interaction with Pb²⁺ (red), Co²⁺ (blue), and Mn²⁺ (green) ions. The overall spectral profiles are similar, indicating that the main structural framework of LDC remains preserved after adsorption. However, subtle yet significant shifts in specific absorption bands and

Fig. 5. The results of EDS, elemental mapping and SEM of LDC within interaction of heavy metals based on (a) LDC before adsorption, (b) Pb^{2+} onto LDC, (c) Co^{2+} onto LDC, and (d) Mn^{2+} onto LDC. Conditions: Mass of adsorbent = 3.34 g L⁻¹, V = 30 mL, pH = 5, Time = 30 min, Pb^{2+} -C₀ = 4.15 mg L⁻¹, Co^{2+} -C₀ = 5.79 mg L⁻¹, and Mn^{2+} -C₀ = 5.52 mg L⁻¹.

intensity variations provide evidence of interactions between the functional groups of LDC and the heavy metal ions.

The highlighted region between 900 and 500 cm⁻¹ magnified in the inset shows three key peaks at approximately 780, 680, and 600 cm⁻¹. These bands correspond to bending vibrations and lattice deformations associated with metal–oxygen (M–O) bonds, such as Si–O–M and Al–O–M linkages, where M represents metal ions (Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , or Mn^{2+}). After adsorption, the intensity of these bands increases, and their shapes become slightly sharper, indicating the formation of new metal-associated bonds at the surface (Pasiczna-Patkowska et al., 2025). The band near 680 cm⁻¹ is due to overlapping symmetric stretching of Si–O–Mg and Si–O–Al(VI), while the ~600 cm⁻¹ peak indicates M–O–M bond formation. Slight shifts in these peaks after heavy metal adsorption onto LDC confirm surface interactions, evidencing successful adsorption through changes in both the 600 and 680 cm⁻¹ regions (Pasiczna-Patkowska et al., 2025; Yan et al., 2012). The peak at 780 cm⁻¹, corresponding to Si–C stretching vibrations (Gualandris et al., 1991), also exhibited noticeable changes after heavy metal (specifically Pb^{2+} and Co^{2+}) adsorption onto LDC, further confirming surface interaction and structural modifications during the adsorption process.

In the higher wavenumber region (3000–3700 cm⁻¹), broad bands associated with –OH stretching vibrations remain mostly unchanged, suggesting that the adsorption did not significantly alter the hydration shell or hydroxyl content of the matrix (Su et al., 2009). The sharp peak near 1000 cm⁻¹, typically attributed to Si–O–Si asymmetric stretching

(PI-TSi-GPMS50 structure) (Wahab et al., 2021), also remains consistent across samples, further confirming the structural stability of the LDC framework during metal adsorption.

As illustrated in Fig. 7, the XRD patterns of LDC before to and during heavy metal adsorption showed clear differences throughout the indicated crystallographic planes, indicating various methods of interaction for Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Pb^{2+} . In Fig. 7a, pristine LDC shows clear peaks at (003), (006), (012), (015), (018), and (113). After adsorption, notable changes occur: Pb^{2+} shifts and intensifies the (006) reflection, indicating interlayer expansion and stronger binding; Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} shift peaks positively, causing lattice contraction. Peak (003) shows slight d-spacing changes, while (012), (015), and (018) display reduced intensity. Overall, adsorption modifies both peak positions and crystallinity. The XRD results of LDC in Fig. 7a show that heavy metal adsorption causes peak shifts and intensity changes, most notably at the (006 ≈ 2θ = 26–27°) reflection. A similar trend was reported by Ritonga et al. (2025), where the main red sand peak at ≈26° decreased after heavy metal adsorption, with a concurrent increase near ≈22°. Both studies confirm that heavy metal incorporation modifies reflection intensities and evidences lattice reorganization. Fig. 7b presents the peak shifts (Δ2θ) observed after adsorption of Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Pb^{2+} on LDC. According to Bragg's law ($nλ = 2d \sinθ$) (Bhattacharjee, 2025), such shifts directly correspond to changes in interplanar spacing (d) (Khan et al., 2020). Fig. 7b shows that Mn^{2+} causes the largest positive peak shift, indicating lattice contraction. Co^{2+} also shifts peaks positively but less

Fig. 6. The FTIR results of LDC in interaction with heavy metals based on LDC before and after adsorption of Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} onto the surface. Conditions: Mass of adsorbent = 3.34 g L^{-1} , $V = 30 \text{ mL}$, $\text{pH} = 5$, Time = 30 min, $\text{Pb}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 4.15 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $\text{Co}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 5.79 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, and $\text{Mn}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 5.52 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$.

Fig. 7. The outcomes of (a) XRD patterns of LDC before/after Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Pb^{2+} adsorption; (b) peak shifts; (c) crystallite size via Scherrer eq.; (d) d-spacing of (003); and (e) peak intensity comparison. Conditions: Mass of adsorbent = 3.34 g L^{-1} , $V = 30 \text{ mL}$, $\text{pH} = 5$, Time = 30 min, $\text{Pb}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 4.15 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $\text{Co}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 5.79 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, and $\text{Mn}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 5.52 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. In panel (b): Peak No. 1 → corresponds to the (003) reflection, Peak No. 2 → corresponds to the (006) reflection, and Peak No. 3 → corresponds to the (012) reflection.

strongly, while Pb^{2+} produces slight negative shifts, which can be explained by its smaller hydrated radius that facilitates deeper incorporation into the LDC lattice, thereby expanding the interlayer spacing. These variations confirm that each heavy metal interacts differently with the LDC lattice, altering interplanar spacing and local crystallinity.

Fig. 7c shows the average crystallite size of LDC before and after heavy metal adsorption, determined using the Scherrer equation (Burton et al., 2009). The pristine LDC exhibits the largest crystallite size, whereas the incorporation of Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Pb^{2+} reduces it, as evidenced by peak broadening that reflects apparent crystallite size

decreases. Microstrain may also contribute to this effect, although it was not deconvoluted during the adsorption process. Mn^{2+} leads to the strongest reduction, indicating higher disruption of crystallite domains. Conceptually, the calculation is based on peak broadening: the full width at half maximum (FWHM) (Burton et al., 2009) of XRD peaks is inversely related to crystallite size, meaning broader peaks correspond to smaller crystallites. Fig. 7d presents the d-spacing values of the primary (003) reflection for pristine and metal-loaded LDC, calculated from Bragg's law. Here, the 2 θ positions extracted from peak analysis were converted into interplanar spacings (d), where smaller $\Delta 2\theta$ yields larger d-values. The results show that adsorption of Pb^{2+} slightly increases d-spacing, consistent with local interlayer expansion, while Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} cause minor reductions, reflecting lattice contraction. Fig. 7e compares the maximum peak intensities, determined by selecting the highest counts in each diffractogram. The pristine LDC exhibits intermediate intensity, which decreases significantly after Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} adsorption, suggesting increased disorder (Babu and Seehra, 1996), while Pb^{2+} produces enhanced intensity, implying stabilization or preferred orientation of certain crystallographic planes.

3.7. Competition effects

Fig. 8 presents the results of a competitive adsorption study designed to evaluate the performance of LDC in removing Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} ions under varying initial concentrations. The study examines three distinct scenarios low, middle, and high concentrations and compares both the adsorption capacity (Fig. 8a) and removal efficiency (Fig. 8b) for each ion. The aim is to understand the influence of co-existing metal ions on the selective removal of Pb^{2+} , which is considered the primary contaminant in this background.

In Fig. 8a, the adsorption capacity (q_e , mg g^{-1}) for Pb^{2+} is consistently higher than for Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} across all concentration scenarios. At low concentrations, Pb^{2+} exhibits a q_e of approximately 6.0 mg g^{-1} , while Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} show much lower uptake values of around 1.5 and 1.2 mg g^{-1} , respectively. As the concentration increases, this trend becomes more pronounced: at middle concentrations, Pb^{2+} reaches roughly 7 mg g^{-1} , and at high concentrations, the capacity increases significantly to nearly 14.5 mg g^{-1} , although with greater variability as indicated by the error bars. In contrast, Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} exhibit smaller incremental increases, with Co^{2+} achieving a maximum of about 6.7 mg g^{-1} and Mn^{2+} remaining under 3.34 mg g^{-1} . These results indicate a preferential affinity of LDC for Pb^{2+} , even in the presence of competing ions and at

elevated concentrations. Fig. 8b complements these findings by illustrating the removal efficiency (%) for each ion across the same three scenarios. In the low-concentration condition, Pb^{2+} is removed with the highest efficiency approaching 95% while Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} achieve about 45% and 38% removal, respectively. This selectivity diminishes at higher concentrations: at middle levels, removal efficiencies converge to around 17–25% for all ions, suggesting a saturation of active sites and intensification of competitive interactions. At high concentrations, Pb^{2+} removal drops to nearly 25%, while Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} follow closely at 23% and 16%, respectively. Despite the decreasing trend in percentage removal, Pb^{2+} still maintains a slightly higher removal rate, reinforcing its dominant adsorption behavior on the LDC surface. Together, these results demonstrate that Pb^{2+} consistently outcompetes Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} in terms of both adsorption capacity and removal efficiency under all tested conditions. The preferential uptake of Pb^{2+} is attributed to its higher initial concentration, potentially stronger binding affinity, and favorable physicochemical interactions with LDC functional groups. Notably, the differences in adsorption behavior become more pronounced at lower concentrations, where active sites are more available and selective adsorption dominates. As concentrations increase, competition intensifies, leading to a relative decline in selectivity and efficiency.

In other studies, it has been demonstrated that the adsorption rate and binding strength of heavy metal cations are significantly influenced by factors such as ionic radius and, more importantly, their hydrated radius. These parameters play a critical role in determining the selectivity of adsorption, in conjunction with the specific nature and characteristics of the adsorbent surface, particularly the chemical and structural features of the adsorption centers (Martemianov et al., 2017). For instance, Inyang et al. justified the preferential retention of Pb^{2+} over Cd^{2+} on both studied clay types by highlighting the smaller hydrated radius of Pb^{2+} . This smaller radius enables a more intimate and stable interaction with the clay surface, offering a better spatial fit compared to the larger cadmium ions, thereby enhancing Pb^{2+} selectivity (Inyang et al., 2016).

3.8. Adsorbent regeneration prediction model (ARPM)

The adsorption of heavy metals onto LDC was tested for five replicate sorption-desorption cycles, using $1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ HNO}_3$ as the desorbing solution. The results of the experiments (Fig. 9a and b) show that the adsorption percentage of heavy metals by LDC linearly decreased with

Fig. 8. The results of competitive adsorption of Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} onto in different scenarios based on (a) adsorption capacity and (b) removal (%). Conditions: Mass of adsorbent = 3.34 g L^{-1} , $V = 30 \text{ mL}$, $\text{pH} = 5$, Time = 30 min. low concentrations: $\text{Pb}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 21.24 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $\text{Co}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 11.42 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, and $\text{Mn}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 10.54 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, middle concentrations: $\text{Pb}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 94.38 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $\text{Co}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 50.56 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, and $\text{Mn}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 41.64 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, and high concentrations: $\text{Pb}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 182.15 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $\text{Co}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 97.22 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, and $\text{Mn}^{2+}\text{-}C_0 = 68.67 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, the number of replications = 2.

Fig. 9. The test of reusability of the LDC for the removal of heavy metals based on (a) Removal Percentage vs. cycle as bar charts and (b) Thales-based theorem. Conditions: pH, contact time, and the mass: optimal amounts and Desorbing solution: 1.0 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃.

number of sorption cycles. The largest decrease in removal efficiency was observed for Co²⁺ (~7.7% loss per cycle), and lower for Pb²⁺ (5.8%) and Mn²⁺ (4.9%). Therefore, LDC can be effectively used as an adsorbent for the treatment of heavy metal ions in repeated cycles.

Zhou and Haynes (2011) explored the mechanisms and conditions affecting desorption by acids. They found that low pH levels facilitate the release of metal cations, as acidic conditions promote the dissolution of Fe and alkoxide/silicate adsorption surfaces, leading to the release of adsorbed metals and surface deposits. Additionally, the strong competition between H⁺ ions and metal cations for adsorption sites causes the displacement of cations in acid solutions. Moreover, acids react with residual alkalinity, which reduces adsorption capacity (Zhou and Haynes, 2011). However, the exact mechanism of repulsion was not explained in their study. Therefore, the reduction of adsorption capacity after a specific cycle can be related to reactions between acidic and basic environments in the present research. In a related study, Iqbal et al. (2002) investigated the removal of heavy metals from PFP using 0.1 M HCl over three cycles. They found that the removal efficiency for most of the heavy metals studied was over 90%.

The current study employed the ARPM computational method to calculate the cycle of LDC regeneration for each metal ion, as presented in Table 4. The C_s values are standard allowable concentrations of heavy metal ions in river water as per World Health Organization (WHO) protocol (Rozana et al., 2020; Waghmare et al., 2015). Additionally, the initial concentration of heavy metals (C₀) in the effluent of a wastewater treatment plant located in Toos industrial park (Mashhad, Iran) was demonstrated in Table 4, based on field surveying.

Based on ARPM results presented in Table 4, it is recommended to regenerate LDC for Co²⁺ and Mn²⁺ after a minimum of three cycles of adsorption to ensure resilience in sequential reactions. The maximum regeneration cycle with nine sequential reactions is associated with Pb²⁺. Therefore, it can be concluded that ARPM is suitable for predicting the cycle of regeneration for each adsorbent and can provide satisfactory

Table 4

The initial concentration of heavy metal, the allowable standard concentration of heavy metals and the cycle of adsorbent regeneration, C₀: Initial concentration of heavy metal ions and C_s: standard allowable concentrations of heavy metal ions in river water as per WHO protocol (Rozana et al., 2020; Waghmare et al., 2015).

Ions	Pb ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Mn ²⁺
C ₀ (mg L ⁻¹)	0.025	0.15	0.9
C _s (mg L ⁻¹)	0.01	0.05	0.5
Regeneration Cycle	9	3	3

results. The validation of the extended ARPM model is illustrated using experimental data for Co²⁺ and Mn²⁺ in Fig. S5. For Co²⁺ with an initial concentration of 0.15 mg L⁻¹, the concentration decreased to 0.07 mg L⁻¹ after five adsorption–regeneration cycles. By the third cycle, the concentration reached 0.0495 mg L⁻¹, nearly equal to the standard limit of 0.05 mg L⁻¹. A similar trend was observed for Mn²⁺ (C₀ = 0.9 mg L⁻¹), which declined to 0.504 mg L⁻¹ after three cycles, aligning with the threshold of 0.5 mg L⁻¹. Beyond these points, further cycles would result in effluent concentrations exceeding acceptable limits. These results validate the ARPM framework, demonstrating its ability to accurately predict regeneration limits based on key parameters: initial ion concentration, water quality standards, the linearity of regeneration decline, and cycle count.

It is worth noting that the calculations and mathematical models outlined in this section of research offer a valuable tool to determine the regeneration cycle of LDC when faced with unknown water or wastewater samples. By simply inputting the initial concentration values of heavy metals found within the samples, one can precisely calibrate the minimal time for the regeneration. This functionality holds immense significance not only for LDC but can also be extrapolated to various adsorbent types and their interactions with different pollutants. This capability becomes particularly important in waste materials applications, where real-world performance data can greatly enhance water and wastewater treatment processes. Understanding how these materials perform in practical settings allows for the maintenance of peak operational efficiency. Given the cost considerations associated with replacing materials, especially within the operation section of water treatment systems, preserving the longevity of adsorbents becomes paramount. By leveraging the insights garnered from these models, operators can effectively manage resources while upholding high treatment standards.

The regeneration of LDC adsorbents using acids such as HNO₃ involves three primary mechanisms, as illustrated in Fig. S6. The first mechanism, proton exchange, occurs when HNO₃ introduces H⁺ ions that effectively replace adsorbed metal ions on the surface of the adsorbent. This process is facilitated by the protonation of surface functional groups in the presence of water molecules, leading to the displacement of metal ions (M⁺) from the active sites (Renu and Sithole, 2024). The second mechanism, pH-induced desorption, involves structural changes caused by the acidic environment (Renu and Sithole, 2024). A lowered pH alters the surface charge and disrupts electrostatic or coordination bonds between the metal ions and oxides like SiO₂, Al₂O₃, and CaO (refer to XRF characterization of LDC), resulting in the release of metals. Lastly, in the solubilization step, desorbed metals are dissolved into the regenerant solution, restoring the active sites of the

adsorbent for reclamation (Renu and Sithole, 2024). Together, these mechanisms ensure efficient regeneration and reutilization of the LDC material in successive treatment cycles.

Regeneration of adsorption using acids provides high efficiency in desorbing heavy metals, as acidic agents such as HCl, HNO₃, and H₂SO₄ effectively dissolve metal-adsorbent (e.g., biochar) complexes and reduce pore blockage from insoluble precipitates, thereby restoring adsorption capacity and occasionally enlarging the surface area to expose new active sites. This makes acid treatment generally superior to alkaline agents in the initial cycles, delivering strong desorption performance. However, repeated acid use presents notable drawbacks, as strong acids, particularly HNO₃, degrade the adsorbent structure by dissolving minerals and damaging functional groups, which progressively reduces adsorption efficiency. Moreover, acid regeneration produces secondary effluents rich in metals and acidity, posing risks of secondary pollution and necessitating additional treatment. In industrial applications, this drawback becomes especially critical. Thus, while acids enhance regeneration efficiency, they compromise long-term stability and sustainability, which should be considered a limitation of the present investigation (Alsawy et al., 2022).

Fig. S7(a-d) provide a comprehensive view of regeneration dynamics for Pb²⁺, Co²⁺, and Mn²⁺ in water treatment operations. Fig. S7(a) illustrates the efficiency decline across cycles, enabling managers to plan regeneration before performance drops below acceptable levels. Fig. S7 (b) compares influent concentrations with WHO standards, where Mn²⁺ emerges as a priority pollutant requiring strict control. Fig. S7(c) highlights average relative decline rates, stressing the need for material selection and scheduling strategies to extend adsorbent lifetime. Finally, Fig. S7(d) presents a heatmap of removal performance, where critical low-performance zones are easily identified, guiding proactive maintenance. Collectively, these results equip plant managers with actionable insights, linking laboratory findings to operational planning, regulatory compliance, and cost-effective regeneration management.

3.9. Sustainable materials management model (SMM)

Various adsorbents are used for heavy metal decontamination, with GO/Carbon commonly employed. Therefore, this research compares the applied adsorbent to the most commonly used materials, such as GO/Carbon. The outcomes of SMM analysis for both GO/Carbon and LCD adsorbents are demonstrated in Fig. 10. The quantitative data for LDC and GO/Carbon materials regarding their environmental impacts are summarized in Table S4, while the results of the indicators in both supply chain and operational categories are presented in Table S5. As per Fig. 10a, it can be understood that in the impact potential category,

some indexes of LDC, including Acid Rain (ACID), Freshwater Aquatic Ecotoxicity (ETOX), Human Health – Respiratory Effects (HRSP), Human Health – Toxicity (HTOX), Ozone Depletion (OZON), and Smog Formation (SMOG) were more appropriate than GO/graphite adsorbent. While in the category, the maximum difference was related to ETOX and HTOX with 64 % and 51 %, respectively. Therefore, it can be concluded that from toxicity aspects, the LDC is safer in comparison of GO/Carbon adsorbents. Likewise, the analysis illustrated that the Eutrophication (EUTR) index of GO/Carbon is much lower than LDC adsorbent (Kim and Chae, 2016).

Also, in the category of Resource Use, water (WATR) and energy (ENRG) consumptions of LDC performed better than GO/Carbon with 12 % and 44 % difference, correspondingly. However, the computations demonstrate that the Minerals and Metals Use (MNRL) and Land Use (LAND) values of GO/Carbon were enormously lower than LDC one. However, there is a sensitive point about the comparison of both the materials as adsorbents. The GO/Carbon should be synthesized from raw materials, while the LDC which is used in this study is waste material of CDW category. It can be understood that with the assumption, both indexes of MNRL and LAND of LDC could not be worse than GO/Carbon because no specific area and minerals are applied for fabricating the wastes.

From the Commercial Resource Conservation and Recovery Act-RCRA Hazardous Waste (CRHW) aspect, the LDC was 26 % better than GO/Carbon adsorbent as per the computations. However, for both Commercial Construction and Demolition Debris (CCDD) and Commercial Municipal Solid Waste (CMSW), the model showed that the GO/Carbon is better than LDC. In the simulation, the LDC is defined as a concrete product, but in reality, it is a waste of concrete product. Therefore, considering the waste management practices of LDC, the overall condition of waste generated (CRHW, CCDD, and CMSW) in the LDC category would be better than that of GO/Carbon.

Fig. 10b and c show the environmental impacts of different SMM indexes in both LDC and GO/Carbon cases as per supply chain and operational categories. Supply Chain refers to the full set of processes required to provide a good or service, whereas Operations handles problems that can occur from the releases of production, the use of resources, and the creation of waste at the facilities (US EPA, 2020).

The analysis of the supply chain (Fig. 10b) demonstrates that just in water consumption and CMSW, concrete products have better condition in comparison to GO/Carbon. The LDC waste is not initial material, but it is repurposed CDW, which is applied again for water purification. In the following, these values of environmental indicators and their effects can be adjusted with management coefficients and rough estimates. Fig. 10c demonstrated that in most environmental impact factors, the

Fig. 10. The outcomes of SMM analysis based on (a) environmental impacts, (b) supply chain contribution (%), and (c) operational contribution (%) in different categorizations. Description: Acid Rain (ACID) (kg SO₂-eq); Freshwater Aquatic Ecotoxicity (ETOX) (CTUe); Eutrophication (EUTR) (kg N-eq); Greenhouse Gases (GHG) (kg CO₂-eq); Human Health – Cancer (HCAN) (CTUh); Human Health – Noncancer (HNCN) (CTUh); Human Health – Respiratory Effects (HRSP) (kg PM_{2.5}-eq); Human Health – Toxicity (HTOX) (CTUh); Ozone Depletion (OZON) (kg CFC-11-eq); Smog Formation (SMOG) (kg O₃-eq); Energy Use (ENRG) (MJ); Land Use (LAND) (m²-yr); Minerals and Metals Use (MNRL) (kg); Nonrenewable Energy Use (NNRG) (MJ); Renewable Energy Use (RNRG) (MJ); Water Use (WATR) (m³); Hazardous Air Pollutants (HAPS) (kg); Metals (METL) (kg); Pesticides (PEST) (kg); Commercial Construction and Demolition Debris (CCDD) (kg); Commercial Municipal Solid Waste (CMSW) (kg); Commercial RCRA Hazardous Waste (CRHW) (kg); Jobs Supported (JOBS); Value Added (VADD) (\$).

LDC wastes are more appropriate than GO/Carbon. Just about LAND, WATR, CCDD, and CMSW GO/Carbon were more suitable than the concrete products. However, considering the fundamental waste of the LDC, it can be concluded that in all the indexes, the condition of LDC is better than GO/Carbon.

Scaling up LDC production from AAC waste may involve challenges such as ensuring material consistency and managing energy inputs. For managing spent LDCs loaded with heavy metals, incorporation into cement-based solidification/stabilisation (S/S) systems is an effective strategy. As described by [Chen et al. \(2009\)](#), heavy metals interact with cement hydration products via sorption, precipitation, and chemical incorporation. For example, calcium-silicate-hydrate (C–S–H) gels serve as key binding phases. Heavy metals may also form double hydroxides with calcium, promoting further hydration. These mechanisms significantly reduce leachability, making cement-based S/S a viable method for stabilizing metal-loaded cement-based materials like LDC and preventing environmental contamination ([Chen et al., 2009](#)). [Masood et al. \(2001\)](#) propose recycling demolished concrete waste by partially replacing cement and fine aggregates in new mixes. Their results show that up to 20 % replacement maintains 75–77 % of conventional concrete strength. This strategy reduces the use of natural aggregates and provides environmental and economic benefits, supporting waste concrete as a viable construction material.

Scaling up adsorbent pervious concrete for commercial applications presents significant technical challenges that must be carefully managed. The research of [Teymouri et al. \(2025\)](#) indicates that optimal mix designs typically require aggregate contents of 1400 kg/m³ using 4.75–9.5 mm sized particles, cement contents of 280–330 kg/m³, and water-to-cement ratios between 0.25–0.45 to achieve the necessary balance between structural integrity and filtration performance. The porosity must be maintained within 15–25 % to ensure adequate permeability (0.14–1.22 cm/s) while preserving compressive strength in the 3–28 MPa range, though these properties follow an inverse relationship with correlation coefficients up to $R^2 = 0.92$. Contamination removal efficiency can reach to acceptable values for heavy metals and 90 % for Chemical Oxygen Demand/ Biochemical Oxygen Demand (COD/BOD) when fine adsorbents like zeolite or LECA are incorporated at 5–15 % replacement levels. However, long-term performance data reveals that infiltration rates decline approximately 10 % annually for the first four years due to clogging, necessitating maintenance protocols. The scale-up process requires precise quality control systems to maintain consistent aggregate gradation, proper mixing sequences to ensure uniform adsorbent distribution, and field curing procedures that preserve the interconnected pore structure essential for both structural performance and water treatment effectiveness.

[Table 5](#) presents a comparative evaluation of various cement-based adsorbents for heavy metal removal, focusing on adsorption capacity, optimal conditions, and kinetics. Among the materials, vermiculite concrete modified with ferric oxyhydroxide exhibited the highest Pb²⁺ adsorption capacity at 197.6 mg g⁻¹, reflecting its strong binding potential ([Martemianov et al., 2017](#)). In contrast, crushed concrete

fractions (CCF) demonstrated a lower capacity for Pb²⁺ at 37.9 mg g⁻¹ ([Coleman et al., 2005](#)), though still notable, while LDC achieved 43.1 mg g⁻¹ for Pb²⁺, 15.2 mg.g⁻¹ for Co²⁺, and 23.5 mg g⁻¹ for Mn²⁺, confirming its broad applicability. In terms of kinetics, LDC outperformed all others with a high rate constant of 1.99 g mg⁻¹ min⁻¹ for Pb²⁺, indicating very rapid adsorption, compared to moderate values for Concrete/maghemite nano material (CMnano) (0.524 g mg⁻¹ h⁻¹ = 0.008 g mg⁻¹ min⁻¹) and vermiculite concrete (0.299 g mg⁻¹ min⁻¹). Operational pH varied across materials, with most functioning at pH 5, except CCF, which performed optimally at pH 11.9 ([Coleman et al., 2005](#)) due to its alkaline nature. Additionally, LDC achieved complete adsorption within 20–30 min (Co²⁺ and Pb²⁺: 20 min, Mn²⁺: 30 min), making it highly suitable for time-sensitive treatment, while other materials required prolonged contact times (e.g., 48 h for CCF, 120 min for vermiculite concrete, 24 h for waste cement powder, and 40 h for CMnano). Also, it is worth noting that all adsorbents followed second-order kinetics. Overall, LDC from the present study offers a promising balance of efficiency, speed, and versatility across different heavy metal contaminants.

CDWs have been widely applied for heavy metal adsorption in various applications, most of which involve soil-based components such as CaO and SiO₂ ([Ranaweera et al., 2023](#)). In contrast, LDC is designed to achieve lighter weight with structural engineering benefits ([Chen et al., 2019](#)). To meet this objective, materials such as Al₂O₃ are incorporated into the LDC mixture, which increases porosity. Enhanced porosity facilitates improved mass transfer mechanisms for heavy metals and other contaminants, thereby strengthening the adsorption performance ([Gong et al., 2023](#)). Additionally, the addition of Al₂O₃ not only alters the physical structure but also influences the chemical specification of LDC, resulting in additional effects on the adsorption process, particularly for heavy metals ([Mola-Abasi et al., 2018](#)). Thus, the preparation of LDC originally intended for structural engineering purposes such as lightweight construction and improved seismic performance also provides both physical and chemical advantages on the adsorbent surface, making it highly effective for heavy metal decontamination.

Finally, the limitation of the present study are:

- The ARPM was validated only under controlled laboratory conditions; external or cross-system validation is still required in future studies.
- Acid-based regeneration suggests the Thales model applies mainly under physical sorption with linear reduction, limiting its applicability in non-linear conditions.
- Experiments were conducted in duplicate ($n = 2$), which may limit reproducibility and should be validated with higher replication in future work.

4. Conclusion

According to the principles of integrated solid waste management, the utilization of waste materials is an important issue. In this study, AAC waste, which is one of the primary construction wastes in Iran,

Table 5

The summary of CDW applications as adsorbent for decontamination of heavy metals in different studies.

Adsorbent	Contamination	Adsorption capacity (mg.g ⁻¹)	Optimal contact time (min)	Operational pH	Kinetics order	Kinetics Coefficient (g.mg ⁻¹ .min ⁻¹)	Ref.
Waste cement powder	As ⁵⁺	28.3	1440	10–11	—	—	(Sasaki et al., 2014)
Concrete/maghemite nano material (CMnano)	As ⁵⁺	11.12	2400	5	PSO	0.008	(Hernández-Flores et al., 2018)
Vermiculite concrete modified with Ferric oxyhydroxide	Pb ²⁺	197.6	120	5	PSO	0.299	(Martemianov et al., 2017)
Crushed Concrete Fractions (CCF)	Pb ²⁺	37.9	2880	11.9	—	—	(Coleman et al., 2005)
LDC	Pb ²⁺	43.1	20	5	PSO	1.99	The present study
	Co ²⁺	15.2	20	5	PSO	0.076	
	Mn ²⁺	23.5	30	5	PSO	0.49	

India, China, and other developing countries, was modified to create an efficient adsorbent for the removal of heavy metals and converted into LDC. This approach aligns with some environmental platforms, such as Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which promote the use of waste materials as adsorbents. The analysis demonstrated that the optimal pH of 5 and minimal mass of adsorbent 6.66 gL^{-1} for adsorption of Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} onto LDC were equal. Also, the minimum contact time for reasonable equilibrium adsorption of Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} are 20 min and 30 min, respectively. The isothermal modeling demonstrated that Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} adsorption onto LDC wastes occurs physically as multilayer adsorption on a heterogeneous surface. Moreover, the kinetic analysis confirmed that the adsorption of Pb^{2+} onto LDC occurs faster than that of Mn^{2+} and Co^{2+} , and the reactions follow a PSO mechanism. Moreover, the competitive adsorption tests revealed that LDC exhibits a higher selectivity for Pb^{2+} compared to the other ions. According to the ARPM, lead has the highest regeneration threshold of nine cycles among all the heavy metal ions under study, while cobalt and manganese have the lowest and is not advised for more than three regeneration cycles. Furthermore, EPA's SMM model indicates that LDC waste is more sustainable than other adsorbents like GO and carbon-based materials.

In future studies, evaluating the efficacy of waste materials in heavy metal decontamination procedures may benefit from the use of machine learning algorithms. Also, in this study, acid-based regeneration indicates that the Thales-based model applies mainly where physical sorption dominates, leading to expected linear reduction trends. However, the model's lack of applicability in non-linear conditions could be considered a limitation, and this hypothesis requires further validation in future studies. Moreover, next investigations could validate heavy metal removal by LDC in real wastewater, assess risks of leaching from spent LDC, and conduct full Life Cycle Assessment comparing its sustainability with other adsorbent materials.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mohammad Gheibi: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Seyyed Roohollah Masoomi:** Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Mohammad Eftekhari:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mehran Akrami:** Methodology, Conceptualization. **Martin Palušák:** Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Daniele Silvestri:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Miroslav Černík:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Stanisław Waclawek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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